

Didactic Strategies for the Use of Artificial Intelligence as a Tool for Dynamic Learning

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 01 October 2025	This study presents the planning, application, and evaluation of teaching strategies supported by artificial intelligence as a pedagogical resource to promote dynamic learning in high school students at Colegio Anáhuac, S.C., Tulancingo campus. Based on an initial diagnosis, four strategies were designed to promote critical thinking, information management, self-regulation of learning, and responsible use of digital tools. The findings reflect a favorable reception by both students and teachers, highlighting advances in autonomy, active participation, and technological appropriation. Consequently, it is confirmed that the integration of artificial intelligence into educational processes represents a relevant and effective option for responding to the challenges of current education, provided that its implementation is based on ethical and didactic principles.
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I. INTRODUCTION

The incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI) into education has led to significant changes in teaching and learning processes, establishing itself as a tool with great potential to respond to the demands of contemporary society. However, its implementation poses challenges that require critical, ethical, and formative integration aimed at strengthening key competencies such as critical thinking, information management, self-regulation of learning, and the responsible use of digital technologies. In this scenario, upper secondary education faces the challenge of taking advantage of the opportunities offered by AI, while at the same time preventing risks such as uncritical dependence or the loss of meaningful pedagogical interaction.

This article presents the development, implementation, and evaluation of teaching strategies based on artificial intelligence, designed to promote dynamic learning in upper secondary education students at Colegio Anáhuac, S.C., Tulancingo campus. Based on a contextual diagnosis that revealed an empirical and limited use of AI in the classroom, four strategies were designed to promote educational innovation and technological appropriation in a conscious and responsible manner. These proposals are based not only on the integration of digital resources, but also on pedagogical and ethical principles that emphasize the role of teacher support as a mediator of the educational process.

The analysis presented allows us to recognize AI as a relevant alternative for enriching educational processes at the upper secondary level, provided that its application is based on ethical, didactic, and methodological guidelines. In this way, the research is part of the search for teaching strategies that promote dynamic learning and contribute to the comprehensive education of students with teacher support and guidance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical framework constitutes the conceptual basis that guides this research, integrating the contributions of international, national, and local authors with the main contemporary approaches to digital education and the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning processes.

A. Education in the digital age has undergone a profound transformation driven by Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). These tools have redefined the dynamics of teaching, fostering a “participatory culture” in which students take an active role in constructing their learning. This implies recognizing the differences between “digital natives” and “digital immigrants” and the technological gaps that condition equitable access to knowledge [1]. In this context, teachers are no longer mere transmitters of content but become facilitators of learning, promoting autonomy and critical thinking in inclusive and collaborative environments.

B. Technological teaching strategies have enhanced more dynamic and meaningful educational experiences. The use of online learning platforms, interactive multimedia resources, and simulations encourages participation and constructive learning, while overcoming geographical and temporal barriers [2]. These strategies also lay the foundation for personalized learning, adapting content and pace to the individual needs of students.

C. Artificial intelligence in education is emerging as one of the most influential innovations in recent years. It is defined as “the design of machines or systems that mimic human cognitive functions, such as perceiving, processing, analyzing, organizing, anticipating, interacting, solving problems, and, more recently, creating” [3]. Complementarily, AI “is a technology capable of simulating human processes of thinking, problem solving, and learning,” which allows for the transformation of multiple dimensions of everyday life, including education [4].

D. Personalizing learning. Using algorithms that process large volumes of data, intelligent systems can identify patterns of student performance and offer differentiated support. This translates into more inclusive educational experiences tailored to the needs of each student [5]. UNESCO emphasizes that these technologies, by generating content in various formats and supporting research, represent an unprecedented opportunity to improve educational quality, although it warns of the need for regulatory frameworks that guarantee equity, ethics, and data privacy [6].

E. AI as a complementary tool to the educational process, without replacing the work of teachers or the development of essential human skills. The true value lies in its pedagogical use, which “is much more important than what the teacher does with computers than the programs themselves” [7] [8]. Consequently, the critical and conscious integration of AI in classrooms requires both teacher creativity and ethical guidelines to guide its responsible implementation.

F. The pedagogical and ethical implications are a central focus of reflection. The need for safeguards to prevent the misuse of personal data and reduce the digital divide [9]. AI can contribute to the development of digital skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving, provided that it is integrated into a pedagogical framework that prioritizes the humanization of technology [10].

III. METHODOLOGY

The research was carried out through an intervention project, understood as “a set of planned actions aimed at generating positive change in a specific problematic situation” [11]. The purpose of this methodological approach was to transform the educational reality through organized strategies that responded to a specific need. To this end, we began with a diagnosis that allowed us to understand the context and establish priorities, followed by the design of an

action plan with the application of appropriate documentary research methodologies and the allocation of resources. In addition, an assessment was considered to measure the impact of the intervention and adjust the process as necessary, along with a validation of the data collection instruments based on four structured digital surveys with dichotomous “yes/no” response options via Google Forms. The first two surveys were administered to obtain an initial diagnosis of AI use, one aimed at teachers with 12 items, and one aimed at students with 12 items. Subsequently, two more surveys were administered to the same study subjects to ascertain their perception and experience of the use of AI-based teaching strategies, one aimed at teachers with 13 items and the other aimed at students with 15 items. In addition to the above, the intervention project was disseminated and validated by experts in the field with similar publications in different educational institutions in Mexico and Latin America [12] [13] [14] [15].

The context of application was developed at the Colegio Anáhuac, SC. Tulancingo Campus, a private institution of higher and secondary education located in Tulancingo, Hidalgo, Mexico. The population consisted of 52 second-semester high school students (groups A, B, and C) and 10 teachers who voluntarily agreed to participate in the intervention project [16].

The project was structured in four phases: diagnosis, planning, implementation, and evaluation, as shown in Table 1.

Tabla 1

Fases por implementar durante proyecto de intervención

Diagnóstico	Planificación	Aplicación	Valoración
• Identificar necesidades	• Objetivos	• Desarrollo del proyecto	• Qué se ha logrado
• Contexto del proyecto	• Metodología	• Seguimiento del proyecto	• Valoración final
• Identificar la población	• Tiempo • Recursos	• Control del proyecto	

During the diagnostic stage, the main educational needs were identified, including students' tendency toward superficial learning, characterized by the search for quick answers rather than the promotion of critical thinking and research skills. Likewise, some teachers' resistance to the use of new technologies was recognized, which represents a barrier to educational innovation.

For the planning phase, the general objective and specific objectives were defined, which guided strategic actions around the use of artificial intelligence in teaching-learning processes. The project was carried out during the January–June 2025 school year, with mainly technological, human, and methodological resources, including the use of the internet, electronic devices, virtual assistants, and data analysis tools.

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In the implementation phase, the actions programmed in the action plan were carried out, with progress being recorded in a timely manner and the strategies implemented being evaluated.

Finally, in the assessment phase, the outcome of the intervention project was determined qualitatively, identifying the desirable and undesirable aspects based on the findings obtained.

IV. RESULTS

The implementation of the four teaching strategies based on artificial intelligence (AI) at Colegio Anáhuac, Tulancingo Campus, allowed for an assessment of their effectiveness in promoting dynamic and ethical learning. The results, obtained through surveys administered to 10 teachers and 52 students, showed positive acceptance of these practices, although they also pointed to areas that need strengthening.

In the open dialogue strategy on AI, 80% of teachers said they had promoted spaces for reflection in class, which showed a willingness to integrate critical conversations on the subject. However, only 20% considered that their students understood the responsible use of these tools, which highlights the need to reinforce the ethical and educational dimension of such discussions.

The strategy of integrating AI into pedagogical activities reflected a notable interest among teachers: 70% designed activities for analyzing and improving AI-generated texts, and 90% allowed their use in tasks under defined criteria. Meanwhile, 77.6% of students reported having used these tools with teaching guidance, and 79.6% acknowledged that this practice improved their understanding of the topics. However, only 49% participated in text analysis or correction exercises, indicating that the application was still partial.

Regarding the strategy of clear question writing (prompts), consistent implementation was observed. 85.7% of students received instruction on how to develop clear instructions, while 81.6% had the opportunity to formulate specific questions. In addition, 87.8% reported better results when using detailed instructions. From the teaching perspective, 80% guided the development of prompts tailored to learning objectives, which strengthened skills in accurate communication and meaningful use of AI.

The strategy of verification and proper citation showed progress, but also significant challenges. 53.1% of students reported correctly citing the use of AI in schoolwork following standards such as APA 7th edition, and 49% knew how to verify information with reliable academic sources. In the case of teachers, 80% promoted the verification of information and 60% encouraged the use of citation standards, although it was recognized that these practices still need to be consolidated to avoid uncritical dependence and strengthen academic integrity.

The results show that the four strategies promoted the critical, pedagogical, and ethical appropriation of AI in the classroom, contributing to the development of digital skills,

critical thinking, and student autonomy. However, the challenge remains to deepen teacher and student training to achieve a more reflective and responsible use of these technologies. Table 2 shows some of the classroom implementation activities of the four teaching strategies in the use of AI.

Tabla 2
Actividades de implementación de las estrategias didácticas en el uso de IA

Estrategia didáctica	Actividad implementada	Síntesis del desarrollo
Diálogo abierto sobre la IA	Mesa redonda	Reflexión conjunta entre docentes y estudiantes sobre naturaleza, beneficios, limitaciones y desafíos de la IA en educación.
Integración de IA en actividades pedagógicas	Edición de textos generados por IA	Análisis crítico de producciones de IA para detectar errores o sesgos y complementarias con información confiable.
Redacción clara de prompts	Creación y prueba de prompts	Diseño de diferentes instrucciones y comparación de respuestas de IA para resaltar la importancia de la claridad y el contexto.
Verificación y citación adecuada	Ejercicio de verificación y citación	Validación de afirmaciones de textos generados por IA y presentación de resultados con citas y referencias en formato APA 7ª edición.

V. DISCUSSION

The results obtained show that the incorporation of teaching strategies mediated by artificial intelligence (AI) encouraged the active participation of teachers and students, promoting dialogue, the integration of pedagogical activities, the formulation of prompts, and the responsible use of information. However, the findings also reveal significant limitations in understanding the ethical and critical use of these tools. This situation coincides with the fact that students tend to use AI in an instrumental way, without reflecting on its academic and ethical implications [17].

It was identified that, although teachers integrated AI into analysis and critical thinking dynamics, the level of student appropriation was uneven, given that the true potential of these technologies lies in accompanying the educational process and not in replacing pedagogical mediation [18]. In this vein, UNESCO has insisted on the need to generate ethical guidance frameworks to guide the educational use of AI, which is particularly relevant in contexts where regulation is advancing more slowly than classroom practice [19].

The weaknesses observed in the verification and citation of content expose the risks of plagiarism and the importance of integrating digital ethics as part of learning. At the same time, students' positive perception of the usefulness of AI confirms that technological integration in education is now inevitable, although it must be accompanied by values such as trust, autonomy, and empathy [20].

The discussion highlights that AI represents a valuable resource for strengthening dynamic learning, provided that its implementation is supported by teacher mediation, ethical training, and the development of critical and digital skills. This implies moving beyond a purely instrumental view of these tools and advancing toward an educational culture where technology is integrated as a support for human judgment, ethical reflection, and the responsible construction of knowledge.

VI. CONCLUSION

The intervention project demonstrated that integrating artificial intelligence (AI) through carefully designed teaching strategies is an effective way to stimulate learning in upper secondary education. The findings showed that, when incorporated within an ethical, critical, and contextualized approach, AI not only promotes the diversification of teaching practices, but also enhances active participation, critical thinking, and the development of digital skills in students.

It became clear that the implementation of these strategies cannot be understood as isolated actions, but rather as part of a comprehensive process of educational transformation that permanently links technology with the ethical and critical training of the educational community. The initial diagnosis identified limitations in the structured use of AI, which justified the need for more organized and conscious training interventions. Subsequently, the proposal and implementation of four teaching strategies promoted more interactive, collaborative, and personalized learning, with positive results in the perception of both students and teachers.

The study reaffirms that the success of these practices depends largely on teacher training, institutional commitment, and the construction of a culture of responsible use of technology. In this sense, the experience developed not only contributed to the immediate improvement of Anahuac School, but also opens up the possibility of replicating these strategies in other educational contexts, contributing to pedagogical innovation within a framework of ethics and social responsibility.

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